

Management Skills; Gaining Organizational Effectiveness

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Abstract

This article delineates the marked effect of Management skills in gaining Organizational effectiveness in attaining focal objective and latter manifest that how management and organization, together make environment productive and enhance the interpersonal skills. By management artistries such as Leadership skills, Time management, Self-management, motivation, Training coaching, Involvement, Plan, Organize, direct, control, Organization makes Strategic planning, Acquisition integration, Project management, Customized sessions, Meeting facilitation, Culture assessment, Team development. From the literature, a brief history of ongoing researches on the topic will be elaborated to provide the significance of the need to use the management skills in the most effective manner for gaining organizational constructive output.

Keywords: Management skills, Organization planning, Organization effectiveness.

Introduction

The theorization of management ideas and practices as fads and fashion is now well established in the literature (Abrahamson, 1991; Czarniawska, 2005; Rovik, 2011). Abrahamson defined a management fashion as a 'relatively transitory collective belief disseminated by fashion setters that a management technique leads to rational management progress' (Abrahamson, 1996: 257).

The new industrial or service behemoths required tools and techniques making it possible to plan, coordinate, control and decide in spite of size. It is in that shifting structural and institutional context of that 'management' as we know it emerged, became a job and was progressively professionalized. Business schools were setup around the country, starting with Wharton in 1881, and became important actors of this process of professionalization (Khurana, 2007).

Productivity missions, where Europeans 'discovered' American capitalism and more particularly management, expert visits and exchanges all played a part in the progressive acculturation. From 1960s on, the internationalization of American firms and services providers took over as a major diffusion channel (B Czarniawska, 2016).

With the rapid development of economic globalization, the rapid development of science and technology, the diversification of customer needs, organizational survival and development environment is undergoing fundamental changes[4]; enterprises are facing market competition are also more and more changeable and intense. The complexity and variety of environment put forward an unprecedented challenge to the organizational effectiveness of the enterprise, which requires the organization to adapt to the increasingly fierce competition in the aspect of reaction speed, product or service quality, innovation and globalization. So, how to improve organizational effectiveness in the changeable environment, such as adaptability, innovation ability, operation ability and value added ability has become an urgent problem to be solved [5-7] (Yingjun Han and Hongjun Lian, 2016).

Based on several researches, it can be found that how to improve and gain organizational effectiveness through management skills in the dynamic environment has become an urgent need to be sorted out. Identify more and more of management skills, the organization must have a high level of planning and strategies to have the ability to make a mark in the competitive changing environment.

Literature Review

Management Skills

Leadership skills

The plight of situation manifests in the world of business, where it has been contemplated not only a series of corporate scandals and spectacular organizational failures, but also various forms of unscrupulous behavior at workplaces, often on behalf of the organization (Umphress and Binggam, 2011). Likewise the lack of wisdom is apparent in amoral, toxic or ugly practices of leader- and followership (Lipman-Blumen 2005), described by Kellerman (2004) as incompetent, operationally rigid, intemperate, callous, corrupt, insular, and evil. All of these problematic issues and ethical failure to execute moral agency, on the micro-, meso - and macro-levels, indicate personal, socio-cultural and systemic pathologies and deteriorates of unwise practices and realities. These and many other problematic issues require and call for surrogated and transformational responses. Perhaps it is the most important phase in a larger process in the transformation and revision underlying world-view. As such organization and leadership as well as wholesome renegotiation and integration of business and economies into a greater and more caring sustainable society and planetary culture (Wendelin Kupers and David J.Pauleen, 2016).

Factor analytic studies from B.M. Bass (1985) to B.J.Avolio (1993) and from P.Bycio, R.D.Hackett and J.S. Allen (1995), B.M.Bass and D.I. Jung (1997) have identified the components of Transformational Leadership: idealized, influence, inspirational, motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration.

For bye, Transformational leadership enhances an organization by elevating the values of workers, motivating them to go beyond self-interest to embrace organizational goals, and redefining their needs to align with organizational preferences (Ross & Gray, 2006). Furthermore , transformational leadership also contributes to a closely related concept, organizational citizenship which refers to an individual`s willingness to go beyond the formal requirements of the job, to engage in productive functions, and to enhance organizational effectiveness (Koh, Steers & Terbong, 1995; Leithwood, Tomlinson & Grence, 1996; and Nguni, Slegers & Denessen, 2006).

Teacher commitment has been identified as one of the most critical factors for the future success of education and schools (Huberman, 1993). The level of teacher`s commitment is considered to be a key factor in the success of the current educational reform agenda as it heavily influences teachers` willingness to engage in cooperative, reflective, and critical practice. This is due to teaching is a complex and demanding profession. To sustain their energy and enthusiasm for the work, teachers need to maintain their personal commitment to the job (Day, 2000). Teacher commitment has been emphasized in three broad categories: commitment towards organization (belief in and acceptance of organizational goals and values; creates sense of community affiliation), commitment towards teaching profession (positive, affective attachment to work), commitment towards student learning (dedication to surroundings) (Dannetta, 2002). (Sii Ling @ Mee Ling , 2012).

Self-management and Motivation

Management practices can directly impact productivity; many others – like monitoring, goal setting, and use of incentives – are mediated through employee decision-making and effort. If advanced management practices are complementary with higher-ability employees, as seems plausible, then one would expect firms that use these practices to systematically alter both skill composition of their workforce and the structure of their pay system.³ (Stefan Bender, Nicholas Bloom, David Card, Jhon Van Reenen, Stefanie Wolter, 2016)

There have been a large amount of studies indicated that members` turnover would negatively influence the organization`s efficiency, and then it influenced the organization`s efficiency and effectiveness, and then it influenced the achievement of its goal (Price, 2001: Hom & Griffeth, 1995).

As the key quality of the modern character, instrumental rationality gradually occupies a place in daily life. In respect of the individuality, the individual in society usually sets the self-development and its motivation as the

personal values (Wu Luping, 2007). Now the non-profit organization is more widely acceptable at home, it's been a stream to join the non-profit organization. The contemporary volunteers have their expectation when they join the voluntary activities (Hustinx, L. 2001). This means that the members of non-profit organization make contribution based on self-development (Wu Luping, 2007). (Yuting Zang & Young Li, 2016).

In today's competitive world, organizations are consistently seeking new ways to maximize their performance and efforts of their employees. Good organizational climate and employee motivation for the survival and success of organizations is more essential. An innovative organization without creative staff and support work environment, do not belief from the employee creativity (Paramitha and Inarti, 2014). Organizations must ensure in such a way that employees and managers operate all their experience, abilities and capacity to promote organizational goals.

The term "motivation" means effectiveness and manoeuvre. Concerning organization, motivation is internal factor that cause change in behavior and the movement in the direct of the organizational goal. To achieve the organization's objectives should know the motivating factors in human and took action to meet their needs. People have different incitements for their activities, and their priorities' is not the same for everyone (Ashish and Zachary, 2004). Job motivation can be salaries and advantages, vigorously in the organization, job security, interest in the job and good social relations at work, nature of work, appreciation, and fun to work (Keritner, 1999 and Shafiey, 1996). (Sanjar Salajegheh, Ali Moradpour Jaghdari, Morteza Mouslei, 2016).

Training and couching

At the present time, environmental conditions and rules of the competition have become so tenacious, compound, effectual, unsure that organizations can no longer ensure their life and survival merely by changing stratagem, system, structure, technology and so on. Therefore, organizations today need an insurrection in the minds of managers and employees. They should provide the conditions so that all employees can find entrepreneurs spirit and implement their entrepreneurial activities easily, continuously, individually, or in group. (M. Alipour, M. Taleghani, 2016).

To lessen the internal stress of the organization and to increase the workplace performance in giving training bad news case to clarify the manager's role as a leader whose task is sometimes to give bad news to an employee in order to achieve a "greater good or purpose". Furthermore, it is esteemed necessary that training conveys knowledge about the appropriate behaviors for performing task, thus providing managers with the sense of predictability and personal control of situation. (Manuela Richter, Cornelius J. Kong, Christopher Koppermann, Michael Schilling, 2016).

Training in delivering bad health news has been found to improve medical students' and residents' performance and confidence in delivering a diagnosis during role-playing scenarios with peers or actors. (e.g., Baer et al., 2008; Baile et al., 1999; Bonnanud-Antignac, Campion, Pottier, & Supiot, 2010; Rosenbaum et al., 2004). Such training usually conveys Knowledge about the systematic structuring of a bad news conversation with a patient. A prominent example is the SPIKES protocol, which describes step-by-step strategic guidelines for delivering bad health news (Baile et al., 2000; Buckman, 1992).

Involvement

(Denis Chenevert, Genevieve Jourdain, Christian Vandenberghe, 2015) elucidated; Three perspective study on the role of involvement work practices and professional self-image in nursing enlists' turnover. The study professes three dimensions (1) the perception of being a proficient nurse (2) the perception of accomplishing important activities associated with the nurse role, and (3) the perception of being a full comrade of an effective care team. It measures nurses' professional self-image before they enter the organizational context and determine if change of self-image over time can prognosticate by exposure to specific work environment

characteristics. Magnet Hospitals suggest that nursing recruits` expectations ; a work environment that allows them to develop, to be cognizant of organizational changes, to be valued as professionals, and to enjoy autonomy in carrying out their work (Rondeau, 2007).

Management is usually seen as a “maintenance” kind of activities, with the emphasis on the “internal-operations” of an institution, in terms of which managing the organizational affairs efficiently and effectively receive preference (Bush, 2007). This means “management involves dealing with system, structures and the culture of school for effective and smooth day-to-day operations” (Naidu et al.,2011).

(A.M.F. Pelser, C.Van Wyk, 2016) “Teacher involvement/participation in school management has been well researched from different perspectives”. Wadesango (2011) found that there are many advantages of teacher involvement/participation in decision- making and Mokaena (2012) indicated that participation in school management is of critical importance, particularly when it is linked to the effects that teachers` participation might have on school outcomes (Somech, 2010). Teacher involvement/participation in school governance, for the sake of improving decision-making in teaching and learning, thus seems vital (Van Wyk, 2004).

Plan, Organize and Control

Two complementary concepts in environmental system analysis are seldom specified in a general decision support process but are significant advances to progress (Virgilio Hermoso, Jhon Molley, Francis Pantus, N.LeRoy Poff, 2016). First, the principle of Pareto efficiency claims that decisions to enact change cannot make one party better off without making other worse off. This classic concept was used by Koopmans (1951).

An important purpose of koopmans` translation of the Pareto efficiency principle was to influence the design of resource management alternatives mathematically based on problem dimensions without requiring social values orientations from decision makers (Goicoechea et al., 1982).

Self - organizing is based on the concept of subscribing self- managing, learning systems composed of 10- 15 people sharing responsibilities of former supervisor (Trist, 1981). Principle self-organization have been explained in organizational theory literature as : minimum critical specification in terms of high guidance and vision provided by senior management while leaving everyday decisions to the teams; requisite variety in terms of sufficient variety in the combined skills of the team to cater to a variety of business demands (Morgan, 1986). These descriptions, principles, and conditions have direct bearing on the fundamental definition of self-organizing teams. (Hoda et al., 2012, 2013).

Energy management from a broad perspective can be seen as an instrument of general management with a universal set of controls energy consumption and costs to obtain it. With a narrow point of view of energy management – is planned system control and accounting of energy flows in order to minimize energy costs. At the heart of the energy management system approach should be used, which includes seven consecutive stages: The system (dynamics) analysis of general situation of energy consumption in the company; monitoring and assessment of the situation at the present time (in fact); decision- making process on implementation of energy management (Tatyana N. Shatalova, Marina V. Chebykina, Tatayana V. Zhirnova, Elena Yu Bobkova, 2016).

Time management

Claessens et al. (2007) defined time management behaviour as “behaviours that aim at achieving an effective use of time while labelled “facets” (Costa & McCrae, 1992). However, more than two levels can be identified (Digman, 1997), including a level between the domains and the facets, referred to as “aspects” (DeYoung et al., 2007). Although, the facets and aspects are different from each-other but still allow traits differentiation within the big five domains.

Conscientiousness has been described as the tendency to be organized, planful, reliable, responsible and thorough (McCrae & John, 1992). It also has proclivity to settle into work quickly, stay focused on the task at hand, and carry out plans while aspect of orderliness describes an individual who prefers keeping things clean, follows the routine, and pays attention to detail (DeYoung et al., 2007).

Organizational Planning

Strategic Planing

Growing interest in Sub-Saharan Africa`s (SSA) emerging markets (Kleiman and Morrissesey, 1994, pp.122-25; Goldman, 1994; Edwards, 1994; Kibazo, 1995) requires that this lacuna be addressed. The deficiency in attention arises from one set of enthusiasms and two sets of anxieties. The first is due to increasing pressure for researching competitiveness in global business, resulting in a noticeable tendency to chart competitive learning and dynamic change within, and between, high performance Asian Economies (Talwar R., 1993, p.27). The anxieties arise because of the unique political and economic geography of SSA in which poor economic performance has made overall patterns of enterprise strategic management difficult to discern (Austin, 1993; Baynham, 1994). Because of discernible divestment trends in the late 1980s and early 1990s (Bennell, 1990, 1994), the pool of MNEs subsidiaries available in SSA is ‘shrinking’. These anxieties, in themselves, and given the ‘final frontier’ of the world`s emerging markets status accorded recently to SSA (Gettleman, 1996), provide justification for turning the spotlight of scrutiny on MNE`s strategy in countries at the margins of the world economy.

The analysis concerns French MNEs and is based on data from responses to a postal questionnaire to executives previously interviewed for an extensive research project comparing British and French FDI operations in SSA. The research presents an examination of a key construct developed by Ghertman (1988) within the framework of assumptions from the mature and dominant archetypes of organizational strategic decision-making (Eisenhardt and Zbaracki, 1992) and moderated by Schoemaker`s interactive rational behavioural model of co-ordinative efficiency and goal congruency (Schoemaker, 1993, p. 109). The construct delineates the major initiating (making first proposal) and impetus (sponsoring activity) roles played by subsidiaries of MNEs in strategic management of investment/divestment (operating enhancement/closure) of subsidiaries (Peter J. Buckley, Fred Burton and Hafiz Mirza, 1998)

Acquisition integration

For a number of years acquisition activity has gone unabated both in the US and Europe. Yet numerous financial studies, both in the US (Jensen and Ruback 1983) and Europe (Muller, Hughes and Singh 1980; Eckbo and Langohr, forthcoming) tend to coverage on the observation that acquisitions on average do not create value for acquiring shareholders. Though such findings have interesting public-policy implications, their managerial implications are very limited on account of their generality. Strategic management researchers, in response, have attempted to identify variables which might discriminate between different types of acquisition and consequent performance levels. Relative size, market share, and profitability of the target prior to acquisition, have all been analysed as possible correlates of success, but the notion of ‘relatedness’ between acquirer and acquiree has received the greatest attention.

Haspeslagh (1985 and 1986) argues that management style and integration capability plays an important role in persuading or dissuading an organization in its decision over how far potential synergies are to be pursued (Philippe C. Haspeslagh and Alison Been Farquhar, 1994)

Project Management

Project management incorporates motivation and coordination of partner activities through the setting of goals and formulation of plans, combined with monitoring, evaluation, and incentives (Du Chatenier et al., 2010). At

the same time, project management is aimed also at harmonizing the collaborative activity through formal rules and routines (Cyert and March, 1963; Grant, 1996).

Project management endows the focal firm with the capacity to identify and specify the orders of events (Nickerson and Zenger, 2004), which, given the strong exploration element of open amalgamative innovation, is especially important (Nicolette Lakemond, Lars Bengtsson, Keld Laursen and Frenndrik Tell, 2016)

IT governance is the organizational capacity exercised by the board, executive management and IT management to control IT strategy formulation and implementation and thus to ensure alignment between the business and IT strategies (Grembergen, 2004, 5).

Organizational effectiveness

Customized session

Individuals need everything to be customized and as indicated by their taste. The use of information in the World Wide Web is growing rapidly; web crawlers must have ability to recuperate information according to customer`s slant. Web lists are created to serve all customers, self-sufficient of the unprecedented needs of any individual customer.

The web crawler has long turned into the most essential entry for K-closet Neighbor CF (Collaborative Filtering) conventional individuals searching for help calculation for gathering based personalization. (Called data on the web. In any case, as G-snap strategy) clients may encounter disappointment when web crawlers return un essential 2 personalized Web search for Improving Retrieval comes about that do-not meet their genuine Effectiveness. To enhance the Effectiveness, they proposed designing (an item before usage gives one a framework in respect to how item should be. It helps one to lessen mistakes while creating and gives a structure to take a shot at and create. For legitimate execution, to plan different charts like class diagram, data stream graph, use case Graph, Activity diagram, Organizational outline, and so forth. Configuration is the formation of an arrangement or tradition for development of a base mistake programming (Shailesh Dhekane, Archana Shete, Adarsh Deshattiwar, Palvi Rane, 2016).

Meeting facilitation

Meetings are quotidian activity in most organization, seeking to provide a means for decision-making and goal setting, scheduling work, solving problems, and disseminating information (e.g., McComas, Tuit, Waks, & Sherman, 2007; Volkema & Niederman, 1995).

Bang et al.`s (2010) sample comprises only eight top management teams Norway, all in the public sector. Patterns may of course be different outside the public sector or other countries. These studies, while informative, do not include a large segment of meeting attendees and they may be missing key elements of meeting-leader behaviors. Building on these studies of leader actions taken during meetings, an examination of the behaviors of leaders (and attendees) pre- and post-meetings is warranted.

The effectiveness of meeting facilitation reflect four main themes: (1) people (P), (2) Meeting Organization (O), (3) Meeting activities (MA), and (4) Meeting outcomes (Jennifer L. Geimer, Desmond J. Leach, Justin A. DeSimone, Steven G. Rogelberg, Peter B. Warr, 2015).

Facilitation involves roles from four fields of expertise. Implementation-oriented facilitation roles relate to roles in change management (i.e., models such as Kotter`s eight step process for leading change [43] and roles in project management (1.e., models such as the PMBOK guide [45]). Since the fields of change management and project management both refer, one way or another, to the importance of meeting management and taking care of group process through change/project implementation, the support oriented facilitation roles are some- what

embedded within implementation., therefore relate to the roles in the fields of meeting management and group and interpersonal dynamics , which aim at supporting group effectiveness, as well as supporting individuals or team during the implementation of a change/project (Sylvie Lessard, Celine Bareil, Lyne Lalonde, Fabie Duhamel, Eveline Hudon, Jhoanne Gourdreau and Lisa Levesque, 2016).

Culture Assessment

Organization dimension is concerned with the collection of information security-related beliefs, values, assumptions, symbols, norms, and knowledge that uniquely identify the organization. The people dimension is concerned with the behavior of any person within the organization who is in direct contact with information assets. Culture dimension is concerned with the identifiable external elements surrounding the organization that affect its structure and operations.

The human factor diamond presents four domains o human factors that influence information security behavior. The information security culture shall consider each human factor carefully to improve user security behavior. The “preparedness” domain mainly concerned with training and awareness, knowledge acquisition, and change of old practices.

The changeover to adapt information security culture needs to be managed carefully and appropriately to achieve the required strategy goals of creating information asset-secure culture. The ISCF has incorporated change management principles in order to guide the changes that are associated with the development of an information security-aware culture inside the organization and to enhance acceptance of compliance with information security policies and procedures (Areej AlHogail and Abdulrahman Mirza, 2015).

Team development

There have been multiple approaches to Implementing Team Building/development in organization. Martin and Colleagues (2009) characterized team building/development interventions into four different areas: (a) single task oriented protocols such as goal –setting, (b) task oriented- protocols that incorporate multiple psychological constructs, (c) socially-oriented protocols focusing on interpersonal relations, and (d) adventure-based experiences. In their meta-analysis , Martin and Colleagues (2009) concluded that adventure-based TB/TD interventions yield some of the most promising results and , given the like- hood for success, should be considered by supervisors.

According to Bisson (1999), to have a positive effect on cohesion an appropriate sequence of activities in an adventure program comprises: (a) acquaintance activities, (b) de-inhibitizer activities, (c) communication activities, (d) trust activities, (e) group problem-solving activities, (f) low ropes course activities, (g) high ropes course activities, and (h) outdoor pursuit experiences. Using this sequence as a guiding framework, the TB/TD becomes icebreaker to the ongoing activities of the organizational forthcoming situation (Kelsea L.Stewart, Jeremie M.Carreau, Mark W.Bruner, 2016).

Proposed Model: Management Skills: Gaining Organization Effectiveness

The proposed model elucidates that the management as “the art of getting things done through the efforts of other people”. By which an organization actually manage, that is, get things done through others-individually, in groups, or in organizations. Formally defined, the principles of management are the actions that “plan, organize and control the operations of the basic elements of [people], materials, machines, methods, money and markets, providing direction and coordination, and giving leadership to human efforts, so as to achieve the sought objectives of the enterprise.”

Management is required in all activities of organization: Goal orientation, pervasiveness, Multidimensional achievement, managing people, Measuring effectiveness and efficiency, gazing dynamic function, continuously monitoring group activities.

Planning (vision & mission, strategizing, goals & objectives) involves setting objectives and resolute course of action for achieving objectives. It`s a process undeviating of several steps. It begins with the environmental scanning means the planners must be acquainted with the critical contingencies facing their organization in terms of economic conditions, their competitors and customers.

Organizing (Organizing design, culture and social networks) demands developing an organizational structure and allocation human resources to make certain the accomplishment of objectives. It also involves the design of individual jobs within the organization (organizing at the level of the organization requires deciding how best to departmentalize, or cluster, jobs into departments to coordinate efforts effectively.

Leading (leadership, decision making, communication, group/team, motivation) are the social and formal sources of influence that is to persuade action taken by others.

Controlling (systems/process, strategic human resources) entails that performance does not deviate from standards. Controlling consists of three steps; (1) establishing performance standards, (2) comparing actual performance against standards, and (3) taking corrective necessary action.

Management skills build and transmit mission statement (who organization is, what are values), vision statement (what organization want to become), strategy (how to achieve mission), goals & objectives (how to gauge degree of success).

First, mission and vision provide a channel for communicating an organization's purpose and values to all key stakeholders. Second, it creates a target strategy development. That is, one criterion of good strategy is how well it helps the firm achieve its mission and vision. Thirdly, provide high-level guide, and the strategy provides a specific guide, to the goals and objectives showing success or failure of the strategy and satisfaction of the larger set of objectives stated in the mission.

For example, in 2006, Disney acquired Pixar; a firm is renowned for its creative prowess in animated entertainment. Disney summarizes the Pixar strategy like this: "Pixar's [strategy] is to combine proprietary technology and world-class creative talent to develop computer-animated feature films with memorable characters and heartwarming stories that appeal to audience of all ages". Retrieved October 27, 2008, from http://www.pixar.com/companyinfo/about_us/overview.htm. Disney has helped Pixar achieve this strategy through an important combination of structural design choices. First Pixar is an independent division of Disney and is empowered to make independent choices in all aspects of idea development. Second, Pixar gives its "creative"-its artists, writers, and designers-great leeway over decision making. Third, Pixar protects its creative ability to share work in progress, up and down the hierarchy, with the aim of getting it better. Finally, after each project, teams conduct "postmortems" to catalog what went right and what went wrong. This way, innovation gained through new project can be shared with later projects, while at the same time sharing knowledge about potential pitfalls. Catmull, E. (2008, September). How Pixar foster collective creativity. Harvard Business Review, 1-11.

An organization is a basic social unit that has been established for the purpose of achieving goals by dissimilar strategies. The typology of an organization developed by Katz and Kahn is based on genotypes, or first-order characteristics: What is the most basic function those organization carries out in terms of society?¹⁵ these first-order, basic functions are: productive or economic functions, maintenance of society, adaptive functions, managerial/political functions.

Goal statement is gleaned and priorities set in terms of primary function. Management can monitor organizational change when actual function performed differs from stated function. Management must make decision in the light of ongoing situation.

Organizational effectiveness is measured with reference to the ability of an organization or management to respond to threats and opportunities in a timely, effective, purposeful, and accurate manner, with full knowledge of conditions, objectives, opportunities, and threats. An effective organization is able to use its access to historic and real time trends and status information as well as knowledge of alternative strategies available to make decisions at the most appropriate level to achieve the greatest benefit for the organization. Measures of organizational effectiveness are ; Timeliness of decision, completeness of information on status, threats, opportunities and available strategies, effectiveness of assignment of decision making responsibilities and requires resources, methods of assuring the carrying out the decision, follow up and intra-organizational updating management, feedback of all the information generated by the decision.

APHSA's organizational effectiveness (OE) department bring forth management consulting products and services to lend a hand to state and local public human service agencies constantly improve their performance and capacity. In resultant of more than five years of technical assistance to state and local human services agencies, the OE department has developed a core set of models that describes the systematic and systemic work an agency needs to do to maximize its organizational effectiveness, including a set of products and services to assist agencies through learning by doing process to learn the work while closing real life organizational gaps.

Conclusion

There have been several articles which emphasis on management and organizational growth/effectiveness. The purpose of this research is to discern the implicit role of management in gaining organization achievements through clear structural strategies/policies. Though this study presents substantial answers to some unresolved issues in management field, the discussion is illuminated with updated literature and proposed model.

The economy has become global and is steered by innovations and technology and organizations have to transform themselves to serve new customer expectations. The theme`s in the present context area; Management skills, organization planning and organizational effectiveness. In this respect, the organizations need to face the challenges with the new management skills which coordinate, plan and control the work of people so that organizational goal can be accomplished. Management skills reflect a broad cross-section of the important managerial activities that are element of the management functions. Organization needs management to develop some deliberate structure so every person can be assigned clear task. Knowing where to begin is critical, but after thatwhat`s next? Many organization stall at this point. Management skills identify the engagement factors impacting performance, plan to translate the findings into action, responding to the employee input, design process to support action, identify success measures.

Every organization, regardless of industry or country, seeks to be more effective and achieve superior results. Management skills are developed to achieve organizational effectiveness. By concentrating on the ongoing business/organization` requirements, organization works on its management skills to enhance/improve the efficiency and effectiveness of employees as well as organization itself.

Management skills encompasses the managerial efforts in facilitating activities; leadership skills, self-management and motivation, training and coaching, involvement, plan, organize and control, time management and developing personal skills by individuals and groups. This study examines the processes that have received the most concord: Management skills, Organization planning and organizational effectiveness.

Organization effectiveness is measured from encompassing organizational members` perceptions of the degree of the overall success, market share, profitability, growth rate, customer session, meeting facilitation, culture assessment, team development and innovativeness of the organization in comparison with key competitors.

In summing up, Management and Organization are the two assets which cannot work without other, both are dependent on each-other` contributions with different medium (strategies, polices, goal setting, structural hierarchy, environment, culture, employees). The key is to maintain the objective through well-defined structure/ model by emphasizing on enhancing the Management characteristics to the organization achievements.

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